

Workshop proposal

1. Workshop Title

Building Trustworthy Autonomy: Human-Centred AI for Robotics

2. Organizers

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Note: This Workshop is supported by the project “[FAIR - Future Artificial Intelligence Research](#)” - Spoke 1 - funded by the European Union under the NextGenerationEU programme.

3. Workshop Format

The workshop will be **open for submissions** and structured into three main segments:

- **Invited Talks** (1 hour): Three invited speakers will present key research and industry contributions. Each talk will last **15 minutes**, followed by **3 minutes of Q&A**, for a total of **18 minutes per speaker**.
- **Flash Presentations** (30 minutes): A set of **10 selected contributions** (from submitted extended abstracts) will be presented through **3-minute talks**.
- **Poster & Demo Session** (45 minutes): Following the flash presentations, all contributors will participate in an **interactive poster session**, where attendees can engage in one-on-one discussions and view demonstrations (if applicable).

4. Workshop Objectives and Main Topics

The development of autonomous robotic systems powered by Artificial Intelligence is rapidly transforming the way we interact with machines, environments, and data. As these systems become increasingly embedded in critical domains, from healthcare and agriculture to industry and mobility, **trust** and **human alignment** are essential.

This workshop aims to create a shared space for researchers, engineers, and practitioners working at the intersection of **AI, robotics, and human-centred design**. We will explore how to design robotic systems that are not only **technically robust and adaptive**, but also **understandable, transparent, and aligned with human values and goals**.

The workshop will cover both **foundational aspects** (such as explainability, uncertainty management, and human-AI interaction) and **practical implementations** (e.g., robot decision-making in dynamic environments, mission planning, and social interaction). By doing so, we aim to foster discussions on how to move from isolated technical solutions toward **integrated architectures** that support **trustworthy autonomy** in real-world scenarios.

Topics include (but are not limited to):

- Trustworthy and explainable AI for robotic perception, planning, and control
- Human-robot interaction and shared autonomy
- Learning from human feedback, demonstration, or natural language
- Embodied intelligence and awareness in unstructured environments
- Task decomposition, mission management, and decision support
- Social, ethical, and regulatory dimensions of autonomous robots
- Architectures for integrating human-centred AI principles in robotics

This workshop also encourages contributions that address the **future directions** of research and policy around **Human-Centred AI** and its concrete impact on the design of next-generation robotic systems.

5. Keywords

Human-Centred AI, Trustworthy AI, Robotics, Explainability, Human-Robot Interaction, Embodied Intelligence

6. Preferred Date

October 18th (afternoon preferred if possible)

7. List of Speakers

- Francesco Marcelloni, University of Pisa - CONFIRMED
 - [Personal page](#)
 - [Foundation FAIR](#)
- Giordana Bucchioni, University of Pisa, AI applications in space robotics – CONFIRMED
 - [Personal page](#)
 - [MUSAPOEM Project](#)
- Matteo Razzanelli, Proxima Robotics, Barriers and difficulties of trustworthy AI in industry - CONFIRMED
 - [Personal page](#)
 - [Proxima Robotics](#)

8. Expected Number of Attendees

10 attendees + invited guests

9. Target Audience

Researchers, PhD students, engineers, policy makers, and robotics professionals from academia and industry.

10. Workshop Outcomes

- I-RIM3D conference proceedings
- Video recordings of talks (if permitted)
- Networking opportunities for collaborative projects and proposals

11. Plan for Special Issue or Session

While we do not currently plan to organize a formal special issue, the workshop is intended as a **first step toward building a dedicated community** of researchers and practitioners interested in **Trustworthy and Human-Centered AI for Robotics**.

The goal is to establish an open network of collaborators working at the intersection of AI, autonomy, ethics, and human-robot interaction. To support this objective, we plan to:

- Facilitate **post-workshop networking**, including a shared mailing list and community space for follow-up discussion and idea exchange
- Collect interest for **future joint activities**, such as invited sessions at upcoming conferences (e.g., ICRA, HRI, ...)
- Explore the possibility of organizing a **focused workshop track or working group**
- Identify opportunities for **collaborative research proposals**, particularly in the context of Horizon Europe calls focused on ethical AI, embodied intelligence, or Industry 5.0

This community-driven approach is intended to **foster long-term collaboration**, support early-career researchers, and align national and European efforts on trustworthy AI in robotics.

12. Call for Extended Abstracts

- Regular extended abstracts submitted to I-RIM and associated to the workshop by the program committee based on topic affinity.
- A call for extended abstracts (2 pages) via EasyChair will be organised. The CFP will be distributed via mailing lists, social media, and institutional channels.

13. Workshop Webpage

A Google site is already designed: <https://sites.google.com/unipi.it/hcai-robotics-workshop/home>

14. Notes on Registration

We will use the two free one-day registrations for the invited speakers or at least for the workshop organizers.